

Supporting Information (SI)

Theoretical insights into the antiradical activity and copper-catalyzed oxidative damage of mexidol in the physiological environment

Nguyen Thi Hoa¹, Mai Van Bay², Adam Mechler³ and Quan V. Vo^{1*}

¹The University of Danang - University of Technology and Education, Danang 550000, Vietnam.

²Department of Chemistry, The University of Danang, University of Science and Education, Danang 550000, Vietnam

³Department of Chemistry and Physics, La Trobe University, Victoria 3086, Australia.

*Corresponding authors: vvquan@ute.udn.vn;

Table of Contents

Table S1. The method to calculate rate constant following the conventional transition state theory	S2
Table S2. Calculated ΔG° of reactions between MD and $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ in aqueous solution, at 298.15 K.	S4
Figure S1. Optimized geometries the selected complexes ($\Delta G^\circ < 0$) in aqueous solution, at 298.15 K.	S5
Table S3. The calculated BDE, PA, and IE and ΔG° (kcal/mol) of the MD + $\text{HOO}^\bullet$ reactions following the mechanisms.....	S6
Table S4. Computed ΔH , $\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kcal/mol), tunneling corrections (κ), k_{Eck} ($\text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) and branching ratios (Γ , %) for the $\text{HOO}^\bullet + \text{MD}$ reaction.	S7
Table S5. The calculated ΔG° (kcal/mol) of the $\text{H}_2\text{A}^+ + \text{HOO}^\bullet$ reactions following the FHT and SET mechanisms in the aqueous solution.....	S8
Table S6: The Cartesian coordinates and energies of TS of the reaction between MD with $\text{HOO}^\bullet$ following the mechanisms in the studied environments and the selected complexes at the M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p) calculating method in water	S9
References	S26

Table S1. The method to calculate rate constant following the conventional transition state theory

The rate constant (k) was calculated by using the conventional transition state theory (TST) (at 298.15 K, 1M standard state) according to the equation (1):¹⁻⁵

$$k = \sigma \kappa \frac{k_B T}{h} e^{-(\Delta G^\ddagger)/RT} \quad (1)$$

Where: σ is the reaction symmetry number,^{6,7}

κ contains the tunneling corrections calculated using the Eckart barrier,⁸

k_B is the Boltzmann constant,

h is the Planck constant,

$\Delta G^\ddagger$ is the Gibbs free energy of activation.

The Marcus Theory was used to estimate the reaction barriers of SET reactions.⁹⁻¹² The free energy of reaction $\Delta G^\ddagger$ for the SET pathway was computed following the equations (2,3).

$$\Delta G_{\text{SET}}^\ddagger = \frac{\lambda}{4} \left(1 + \frac{\Delta G_{\text{SET}}^0}{\lambda} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda \approx \Delta E_{\text{SET}} - \Delta G_{\text{SET}}^0 \quad (3)$$

where ΔG_{SET} is the Gibbs energy of reaction, ΔE_{SET} is the non-adiabatic energy difference between reactants and vertical products for SET.^{13,14}

For rate constants that were close to the diffusion limit a correction was applied to yield realistic results¹⁵. The apparent rate constants (k_{app}) were calculated following the Collins–Kimball theory in the solvents at 298.15K;¹⁶ the steady-state Smoluchowski rate constant (k_D) for an irreversible bimolecular diffusion–controlled reaction was calculated following the literature as corrodng to equations (4,5).^{15,17}

$$k_{\text{app}} = \frac{k_{\text{TST}} k_D}{k_{\text{TST}} + k_D} \quad (4)$$

$$k_D = 4\pi R_{AB} D_{AB} N_A \quad (5)$$

where R_{AB} is the reaction distance, N_A is the Avogadro constant, and $D_{AB} = D_A + D_B$ (D_{AB} is the mutual diffusion coefficient of the reactants A and B),^{16,18} where D_A or D_B is estimated using the Stokes–Einstein formulation (6).^{19,20}

$$D_{A \text{ or } B} = \frac{k_B T}{6\pi \eta a_{\text{ or } B}} \quad (6)$$

η is the viscosity of the solvents (i.e. $\eta(\text{H}_2\text{O}) = 8.91 \times 10^{-4}$ Pa s, $\eta(\text{pentyl ethanoate}) = 8.62 \times 10^{-4}$ Pa s) and a is the

radius of the solute.

The kinetic study requires different considerations. Water (dielectric constants, $\epsilon = 78.35$) and pentyl ethanoate ($\epsilon = 4.73$) are the *de facto* standard solvents in the literature to mimic the polar and nonpolar environments in the human body.^{15,21-23} Thus, these solvents were used to model the physiological environments. The solvent cage effects were included following the corrections proposed by Okuno,²⁴ adjusted with the free volume theory according to the Benson correction^{15,25-27} to reduce over-penalizing entropy losses in solution. For the species that have multiple conformers, all of these were investigated and the conformer with the lowest electronic energy was included in the analysis.^{22,23} The hindered internal rotation treatment was also applied to the single bonds to ensure that the obtained conformer has the lowest electronic energy.^{23,28} All transition states were characterized by the existence of only one single imaginary frequency. Intrinsic coordinate calculations (IRCs) were performed to ensure that each transition state is connected correctly with the pre-complex and post-complex.

Table S2. Calculated ΔG° of reactions between MD and $[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ in aqueous solution, at 298.15 K.

No.	Reactions	Positions	ΔG°
1	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{A}^+ \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{A})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{3+}$	1-N	8.3
		1-O	14.1
2	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{A}^+ \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{A})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^{3+} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	2-N	12.2
		2-O	9.6
3	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{A}^+ \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{HA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{H}^+$	3-N	143.9
		3-O	146.6
4	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{A}^+ \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{HA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^{2+} + \text{H}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	4-N	132.3
		4-O	141.3
5	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{A}^+ \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^+ + 2\text{H}^+$	5-N	297.8
		5-O	278.6
6	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{A}^+ \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^+ + 2\text{H}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	6-N	290.8
		6-O	268.8
7	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{HA} \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{HA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$	7-N	-29.0
		7-O	-26.2
8	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{HA} \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{HA})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	8-N	-40.5
		8-O	-31.5
9	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{HA} \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^+ + \text{H}^+$	9-N	-16.4
		9-O	-35.6
10	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{HA} \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3]^+ + \text{H}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	10-N	117.9
		10-O	95.9
11	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{A}^- \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^+$	11-N	14.7
		11-O	-4.5
12	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + \text{A}^- \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	12-N	7.7
		12-O	-14.3
13	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 2\text{H}_2\text{A}^+ \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{HA})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+} + 2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	N	263.2
14	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 2\text{HA} \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{HA})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	N	-82.5
15	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 2\text{H}_2\text{A}^+ \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] + 4\text{H}^+ + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	O	538.1
16	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 2\text{HA} \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] + 2\text{H}^+ + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	O	192.4
17	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 2\text{A}^- \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2] + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	O	-28.1
18	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 3\text{H}_2\text{A}^+ \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^- + 6\text{H}^+ + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	O	811.0
19	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 2\text{HA} \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^- + 4\text{H}^+ + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	O	292.4
20	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 2\text{A}^- \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^- + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	O	-38.2
21	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 4\text{H}_2\text{A}^+ \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)_4]^{2-} + 6\text{H}^+ + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	O	1084.70
22	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 4\text{HA} \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)_4]^{2-} + 4\text{H}^+ + 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	O	393.30
23	$[\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+} + 4\text{A}^- \rightarrow [\text{Cu}(\text{A}^-)_4]^{2-} + 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	O	-47.60

Figure S1. Optimized geometries the selected complexes ($\Delta G^\circ < 0$) in aqueous solution, at 298.15 K.

Table S3. The calculated BDE, PA, and IE and ΔG° (kcal/mol) of the MD + HOO $\cdot$ reactions following the mechanisms.

Positions	HAT		SP		SET	
	BDE	ΔG°	PA	ΔG°	IE	ΔG°
O3-H	84.4	-30.8	342.0	160.8	189.8	137.0
C7-H	86.4	-29.4				
C8-H	100.4	-15.3				
C9-H	90.3	-24.0				

Table S4. Computed ΔH , $\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kcal/mol), tunneling corrections (κ), k_{Eck} ($\text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) and branching ratios (Γ , %) for the $\text{HOO}^\bullet + \text{MD}$ reaction.

Mechanisms		ΔH	$\Delta G^\ddagger$	κ	k_{Eck}	Γ
FHT	O3-H	3.6	13.0	158.7	2.95×10^5	100.0
	C7-H	9.4	18.9	43.3	3.79	0.0
	C8-H	17.6	25.5	33.2	4.34×10^{-5}	0.0
	C9-H	13.3	22.3	495.1	1.33×10^{-1}	0.0
k_{overall}					2.95E+05	

Table S5. The calculated ΔG° (kcal/mol) of the $H_2A^+ + HOO^\bullet$ reactions following the FHT and SET mechanisms in the aqueous solution.

Positions	FHT		SET	
	BDE	ΔG°	IE	ΔG°
O3-H	94.4	4.6	157.4	52.6
C7-H	85.7	-4.4		
C8-H	102.3	11.6		
C9-H	91.2	2.4		
N1-H	105.8	16.2		

Table S6: The Cartesian coordinates and energies of TS of the reaction between MD with HOO^{*} following the mechanisms in the studied environments and the selected complexes at the M06-2X/6-311++G(d,p) calculating method in water

Name				TS-HA-C7-H-OOH-FHT (gas phase)	
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy	
O	-1.26081800	-1.32237600	-1.15449900	Zero-point correction=	0.189145 (Hartree/Particle)
N	1.16768600	0.95072800	0.34769900	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.202158
C	0.01042700	0.49377100	-0.15214600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.203102
C	-1.15502800	1.39380900	-0.05329300	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.148772
C	-0.09073700	-0.78841500	-0.72849200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-592.066799
C	2.27571800	0.22741100	0.22216700	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-592.053786
C	-1.90087800	1.75937400	-1.32291500	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-592.052842
C	1.07041600	-1.53566100	-0.88172100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-592.107172
C	2.26592200	-1.01987100	-0.41416400		
C	3.53906300	0.81869500	0.78662500		
H	-0.92980800	2.24513000	0.58836900		
H	-2.00993300	0.70029900	0.62221400		
H	-2.84297600	2.25931100	-1.09172500		
H	-1.29042300	2.45294900	-1.91020700		
H	-2.10752300	0.88942000	-1.94612700		
H	1.00521100	-2.51427600	-1.34178600		
H	3.18489600	-1.58504200	-0.51288300		
H	3.39419100	1.07628300	1.83709400		
H	4.37590600	0.12480500	0.70439600		
H	3.79351000	1.73821300	0.25546800		
H	-1.99172700	-1.02359300	-0.59230100		
H	-1.86641000	-0.67689500	2.66544600		
O	-2.74176600	-0.20112300	1.08234600		
O	-1.86968200	-1.03104900	1.76612600		
Name				TS-H2A ⁺ -C7-H-OOH-FHT (Water)	
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy	
O	-1.24327300	-1.41979000	-1.14770600	Zero-point correction=	0.201215 (Hartree/Particle)
N	1.15590300	0.89288400	0.24455900	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.214120
C	-0.04900800	0.46077300	-0.21253800	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.215064
C	-1.19553800	1.36970300	-0.10206800	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.160608
C	-0.09878200	-0.83731500	-0.72487500	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-592.524667
C	2.30866100	0.21242200	0.19719000	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-592.511762
C	-1.93479400	1.74969300	-1.36674200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-592.510818
C	1.08004300	-1.58056300	-0.81705900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-592.565274
C	2.27561000	-1.05918800	-0.36772200		
C	3.53155500	0.84383100	0.76717200		
H	-0.99053500	2.21408100	0.55668100		
H	-2.04825400	0.67640000	0.58976200		
H	-2.85471800	2.27788400	-1.11471400		
H	-1.30560200	2.42544200	-1.95504300		
H	-2.18070700	0.89110800	-1.99164800		
H	1.02850100	-2.57942000	-1.23434100		
H	3.19247200	-1.62976900	-0.42878400		
H	3.43061900	1.92835700	0.80686800		
H	3.69112900	0.47077700	1.78220900		
H	4.40013700	0.57770900	0.16612400		
H	-2.02805500	-1.02097000	-0.73833800		
H	-1.86692500	-0.53299800	2.70464700		
O	-2.75851000	-0.19817200	1.09067100		

O	-1.90459600	-0.97457800	1.84067600	
H	1.18517600	1.83539100	0.63539100	
Name				TS-HA-C8-H-OOH-FHT (gas phase)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	-0.34551900	2.16965600	-0.01819600	Zero-point correction= 0.188203 (Hartree/Particle)
N	1.29685000	-1.02211400	-0.21292100	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.201604
C	0.36325000	-0.07914600	-0.20668600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.202548
C	-1.08112500	-0.49872800	-0.35035100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.145703
C	0.68575600	1.27557000	-0.03162200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -592.054174
C	2.58591700	-0.69068400	-0.06671400	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -592.040773
C	-1.74746500	-0.50303200	1.00544000	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -592.039829
C	2.01412600	1.63293500	0.11578800	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -592.096674
C	2.98058100	0.63303800	0.09714300	
C	3.57602200	-1.82235300	-0.09209900	
H	-1.09844600	-1.49599900	-0.78915200	
H	-1.60621400	0.19061400	-1.01571900	
H	-3.02651100	-0.78284200	0.74015900	
H	-1.45152900	-1.31215800	1.67162300	
H	-1.80807500	0.46777000	1.49611700	
H	2.29382400	2.67443100	0.24454600	
H	4.02851700	0.88157100	0.21091700	
H	3.35085500	-2.53432100	0.70420200	
H	3.50628200	-2.35914700	-1.04006300	
H	4.59726600	-1.46241600	0.03503400	
H	-0.00201500	3.06325100	0.06636000	
H	-4.62414500	0.72307900	-0.37924600	
O	-4.12879300	-0.92117700	0.35153300	
O	-4.21320400	-0.07155800	-0.74330100	
Name				TS-HA-C9-H-OOH-FHT (gas phase)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	2.40596500	1.55959500	0.57579400	Zero-point correction= 0.189162 (Hartree/Particle)
N	-0.01248700	-0.93467500	-0.32222900	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.202119
C	1.07650100	-0.34805100	0.14767000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.203063
C	2.15991800	-1.21205900	0.73055000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.148132
C	1.25173700	1.04887700	0.07020100	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -592.060657
C	-0.98480300	-0.19556500	-0.89063600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -592.047701
C	3.27953500	-1.45415600	-0.28935300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -592.046757
C	0.25923300	1.82612200	-0.50671600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -592.101688
C	-0.87648400	1.19697000	-0.99646100	
C	-2.19730900	-0.89013000	-1.31005300	
H	1.70148600	-2.15652200	1.02441700	
H	2.57104200	-0.73192200	1.62146200	
H	4.05580200	-2.09372000	0.13415400	
H	2.88055300	-1.94260800	-1.18057900	
H	3.74031300	-0.51046300	-0.58777400	
H	0.37553100	2.90345800	-0.57954800	
H	-1.67155400	1.76980500	-1.45961400	
H	-2.09709600	-1.96850800	-1.39042100	
H	-2.98695600	-0.72475000	-0.28010900	
H	-2.77060000	-0.41887800	-2.10527700	
H	2.41802700	2.51552800	0.47450600	
H	-2.34135400	0.86271500	1.47242100	
O	-3.56191400	-0.33592300	0.73156100	
O	-2.54376900	-0.07285400	1.61523900	

Name				TS-HA-O3-H-OOH-FHT (gas phase)	
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy	
O	-1.58709000	-0.50950300	-1.26029200	Zero-point correction=	0.189466 (Hartree/Particle)
N	1.24714100	0.77505900	0.54733300	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.202373
C	0.00411500	0.63930400	0.10361600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.203317
C	-1.01192200	1.66124400	0.51460900	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.148909
C	-0.36216700	-0.41056400	-0.79485800	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-592.076016
C	2.19083200	-0.09186700	0.15644200	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-592.063110
C	-1.19137400	2.71302200	-0.58991800	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-592.062166
C	0.63243000	-1.32499000	-1.18525900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-592.116574
C	1.91646900	-1.15965100	-0.71228500		
C	3.56947600	0.14436000	0.69781900		
H	-0.65692300	2.12838000	1.43349100		
H	-1.96754600	1.17495200	0.72019400		
H	-1.91932900	3.46585000	-0.28358700		
H	-0.24437500	3.21534800	-0.79697900		
H	-1.54700200	2.24508100	-1.50964200		
H	0.36092400	-2.12545600	-1.86389200		
H	2.71068700	-1.83641400	-1.00294000		
H	3.91791900	1.13445800	0.39563000		
H	3.54382900	0.13228200	1.78948200		
H	4.27737300	-0.60586300	0.34668300		
H	-2.28102900	-0.80669700	-0.43347200		
H	-1.34370100	-2.16307100	1.48724700		
O	-2.74711400	-1.28959500	0.63270000		
O	-1.67429200	-1.25207900	1.47077200		
Name				TS-HA-O3-H-OOH-FHT (pentyl ethanoate)	
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy	
O	-1.60575100	-0.48729600	-1.26826500	Zero-point correction=	0.188934 (Hartree/Particle)
N	1.24812900	0.75563800	0.54011100	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.201931
C	0.00273000	0.64000800	0.09284900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.202875
C	-0.99057000	1.68812400	0.49383500	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.147804
C	-0.37733700	-0.40963700	-0.79736800	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-592.094253
C	2.17925200	-0.13182500	0.16033100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-592.081256
C	-1.04564200	2.80579700	-0.55617200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-592.080312
C	0.60088100	-1.34624500	-1.17688400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-592.135383
C	1.88553300	-1.20103600	-0.70160500		
C	3.55859600	0.07732400	0.70414800		
H	-0.68008000	2.09302500	1.45821300		
H	-1.98002000	1.24258800	0.61013800		
H	-1.75711200	3.57622800	-0.25270800		
H	-0.06435600	3.27141600	-0.67287900		
H	-1.35960400	2.41269800	-1.52570100		
H	0.32215300	-2.15178800	-1.84718000		
H	2.66774400	-1.89572500	-0.98247800		
H	3.93008900	1.06010800	0.40221100		
H	3.53281600	0.06359100	1.79680800		
H	4.25015200	-0.68801500	0.35311200		
H	-2.29348000	-0.79267900	-0.45434500		
H	-1.35293800	-2.13963800	1.46306700		
O	-2.78051100	-1.28418000	0.61972500		
O	-1.71785300	-1.23806700	1.46806000		
Name				TS-HA-O3-H-OOH-FHT (water)	
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy	

O	1.63592200	-0.45309900	1.24741000	Zero-point correction=	0.189084 (Hartree/Particle)
N	-1.23382000	0.78552000	-0.54873900	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.201929
C	0.01524700	0.66637700	-0.10811900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.202873
C	1.02819600	1.67958300	-0.54416000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.148445
C	0.38954700	-0.36747100	0.80026700	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-592.096052
C	-2.16871300	-0.08735700	-0.13714900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-592.083207
C	1.17832600	2.78521000	0.50964800	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-592.082263
C	-0.58878200	-1.28795300	1.21109400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-592.136691
C	-1.87549400	-1.13926900	0.74561100		
C	-3.55172900	0.10817800	-0.67048900		
H	0.69900000	2.10666700	-1.49209400		
H	1.99206300	1.19142900	-0.70347500		
H	1.91328300	3.52214000	0.18132400		
H	0.22685700	3.29701200	0.66916300		
H	1.50993700	2.37022200	1.46377900		
H	-0.30996500	-2.08533400	1.89055300		
H	-2.66171900	-1.82060000	1.04586800		
H	-3.91102000	1.10869100	-0.41690600		
H	-3.54339900	0.03179100	-1.76098000		
H	-4.24184300	-0.63174500	-0.26769500		
H	2.27044300	-0.85269300	0.43541000		
H	1.11126600	-2.20484600	-1.29704800		
O	2.67835800	-1.40324400	-0.65838900		
O	1.56350100	-1.35305200	-1.43238800		
Name				[Cu(HA)(H₂O)₄]²⁺(site N) (water)	
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy	
O	3.90485800	-0.88104800	0.53722700	Zero-point correction=	0.283128 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.63873900	0.47303500	-0.16387900	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.304884
C	1.62898200	-0.38773000	0.10841900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.305828
C	1.32031600	-1.85514100	0.16088200	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.234629
C	2.94628200	0.05765200	0.27351600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-2387.081057
C	0.90303600	1.78548000	-0.29960500	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-2387.059301
C	1.61664800	-2.52236500	-1.18758800	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-2387.058357
C	3.22753500	1.41037100	0.17368900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-2387.129556
C	2.19087100	2.28151500	-0.12355800		
C	-0.21616000	2.70223000	-0.69720000		
H	0.26880500	-1.97446600	0.41326600		
H	1.91142300	-2.33004400	0.94634400		
H	1.35431100	-3.58173700	-1.15922200		
H	1.04343600	-2.04640800	-1.98714800		
H	2.67673100	-2.43865600	-1.43771000		
H	4.24228600	1.76715700	0.31778900		
H	2.37508800	3.34407700	-0.22251400		
H	-1.14903700	2.40438500	-0.22373200		
H	0.00938500	3.73190400	-0.41917900		
H	-0.35555700	2.67375200	-1.78279200		
H	4.76581800	-0.45033200	0.61568100		
Cu	-1.76574000	-0.19975600	0.13784900		
O	-2.70988200	0.74182400	-1.45022300		
H	-3.13828100	0.08506700	-2.01592100		
H	-2.09798700	1.21872300	-2.02592500		
O	-2.29346700	1.32491300	1.44469100		
H	-2.90837000	1.94056600	1.02287000		
H	-2.76098200	0.98193100	2.21828500		

O	-1.55240000	-1.42642800	1.82103300	
H	-0.72762500	-1.22769000	2.28501800	
H	-2.25428500	-1.27616500	2.46849900	
O	-1.79096900	-1.85766200	-1.07909900	
H	-1.24189100	-1.73823900	-1.86573300	
H	-1.44816600	-2.64702000	-0.63870100	
Name				[Cu(HA)(H₂O)₄]²⁺(site O) (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	-0.29177000	0.39465200	-1.22796200	Zero-point correction= 0.283287 (Hartree/Particle)
N	2.87945500	0.31049100	0.58472400	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.304883
C	1.70996000	0.75586900	0.11571900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.305827
C	1.28011700	2.14292000	0.50797400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.234905
C	0.94635700	-0.02850700	-0.75314500	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2387.076848
C	3.32804200	-0.90244800	0.23360200	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2387.055253
C	1.75711300	3.18735900	-0.50782900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -2387.054309
C	1.39800600	-1.27684300	-1.13869600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -2387.125230
C	2.60968500	-1.72429600	-0.63215700	
C	4.64122000	-1.33660900	0.81692000	
H	1.69779300	2.36162800	1.49155100	
H	0.19071700	2.18358300	0.59974900	
H	1.44282900	4.18734400	-0.20399900	
H	2.84656800	3.17667100	-0.58171600	
H	1.34886300	2.98931700	-1.50313300	
H	0.80980300	-1.87762600	-1.82315800	
H	2.99741000	-2.69708800	-0.90763900	
H	5.43252600	-0.64107000	0.52808600	
H	4.58686800	-1.34041100	1.90803800	
H	4.91174600	-2.33577900	0.47641400	
H	-0.30895800	1.35560500	-1.34912800	
Cu	-2.06722400	-0.20672500	-0.16853100	
O	-1.67829800	-2.18043700	-0.46320300	
H	-1.44177400	-2.35792600	-1.38367100	
H	-0.92081200	-2.47290700	0.06232000	
O	-3.86755400	-0.67334400	0.72740100	
H	-3.94276500	-0.23744000	1.58701000	
H	-3.92488200	-1.62095400	0.90844100	
O	-2.65545300	1.73517000	-0.37046200	
H	-2.04648000	2.36177600	0.04294400	
H	-3.51802600	1.89615700	0.03516000	
O	-1.02093400	-0.19449400	1.88074300	
H	-0.54440900	0.60634400	2.13082200	
H	-1.72934900	-0.27683400	2.53112300	
Name				[Cu(HA)(H₂O)₃]²⁺(site N) (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	3.55309200	-1.27300800	0.47117000	Zero-point correction= 0.257990 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.43337500	0.45418500	0.03169400	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.276794
C	1.32557100	-0.51637900	0.28988700	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.277738
C	0.84053400	-1.90092100	0.60738100	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.212939
C	2.69521700	-0.24425000	0.21922200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2310.671822
C	0.82267900	1.70765200	-0.27440000	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2310.653018
C	0.78380500	-2.77750100	-0.64924900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -2310.652074
C	3.12163200	1.03552300	-0.10008100	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -2310.716874
C	2.17471700	2.01771900	-0.34620300	
C	-0.23900000	2.74358200	-0.49373700	

H	-0.14835400	-1.84224400	1.07002600	
H	1.51254600	-2.34978800	1.34055700	
H	0.46392800	-3.78849200	-0.39125100	
H	0.07509800	-2.36885900	-1.37276000	
H	1.76521700	-2.83862200	-1.12424300	
H	4.18353000	1.25308000	-0.15229100	
H	2.47819700	3.02692500	-0.59314800	
H	-1.05013300	2.34251100	-1.10700100	
H	-0.66390100	3.05462000	0.46446700	
H	0.17853300	3.62045200	-0.98675000	
H	4.46514700	-0.96318500	0.39746000	
Cu	-1.58335400	-0.01799300	0.04854700	
O	-1.55456500	-0.30411100	-1.98440500	
H	-2.06858600	-1.07422900	-2.26334500	
H	-0.66486400	-0.43749800	-2.33886700	
O	-3.46308300	-0.79752700	0.20651700	
H	-4.03459100	-0.26059000	0.77136900	
H	-3.90561800	-0.84137000	-0.65172800	
O	-1.71321200	0.79143500	1.91916900	
H	-0.94618500	0.58820500	2.47151100	
H	-2.48510900	0.49470900	2.41974300	
Name				[Cu(HA)(H₂O)₃]²⁺(site O) (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	-0.41434000	-0.10980400	-1.26433700	Zero-point correction= 0.259100 (Hartree/Particle)
N	2.84620000	0.76358500	0.04969200	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.277470
C	1.60201100	0.86981100	-0.42807900	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.278414
C	0.98552200	2.23854400	-0.50944400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.214183
C	0.89494700	-0.26856500	-0.81666600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2310.657610
C	3.42936200	-0.43980100	0.14470400	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2310.639240
C	0.03959500	2.51395800	0.66322800	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -2310.638296
C	1.47533600	-1.51961200	-0.72841800	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -2310.702528
C	2.77276900	-1.60575100	-0.24435500	
C	4.82981400	-0.47522700	0.68356200	
H	0.44084400	2.33848400	-1.45108000	
H	1.79626700	2.96789100	-0.51075800	
H	-0.32020600	3.54394200	0.63109000	
H	-0.83319800	1.85674700	0.62692700	
H	0.54923600	2.35918200	1.61792900	
H	0.92088500	-2.40030200	-1.03526100	
H	3.27003600	-2.56411700	-0.16299500	
H	5.48924300	0.13384900	0.06102700	
H	4.85654000	-0.06324300	1.69498300	
H	5.21501700	-1.49427200	0.70980000	
H	-0.59279700	-0.73864500	-1.98074200	
Cu	-2.02823800	-0.29760000	0.06102400	
O	-3.19208700	0.09236600	-1.55139000	
H	-4.11906800	-0.13370400	-1.39621900	
H	-2.93096300	-0.37854600	-2.35432000	
O	-3.62479100	-0.51025300	1.31548700	
H	-4.41525100	-0.04654900	1.00865200	
H	-3.42614800	-0.15598500	2.19239800	
O	-0.89834800	-0.66769700	1.71083800	
H	-0.41826100	-1.50328600	1.62363500	
H	-0.21406900	0.00796400	1.82494300	

Name				[Cu(A')(H ₂ O) ₄] ⁺ (site N) (water)	
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy	
O	4.14677000	-0.60095500	0.65501800	Zero-point correction=	0.264556 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.85870700	0.50577300	-0.14468300	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.288487
C	1.84345400	-0.29600100	0.23136400	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.289431
C	1.54947400	-1.73352300	0.49753000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.211951
C	3.22703600	0.17786000	0.32184500	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-2386.606510
C	1.10960200	1.80244300	-0.44724400	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-2386.582578
C	1.79448800	-2.56385200	-0.77288700	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-2386.581634
C	3.45751300	1.56230300	0.00912200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-2386.659114
C	2.41024500	2.34971200	-0.36592400		
C	-0.05192500	2.62544000	-0.87818000		
H	0.50676300	-1.82493000	0.81202900		
H	2.19176800	-2.09398800	1.30208700		
H	1.53271100	-3.60755700	-0.59197300		
H	1.18540200	-2.19160100	-1.59968000		
H	2.84452400	-2.51582500	-1.06819500		
H	4.47085300	1.94088500	0.07787600		
H	2.54944300	3.39471100	-0.61297100		
H	-0.79757600	2.65685400	-0.07695500		
H	0.25095200	3.63963600	-1.13207900		
H	-0.53009800	2.15751600	-1.74505200		
Cu	-1.11133500	-0.24540700	-0.35385000		
O	-2.95190700	1.01747500	-0.66533100		
H	-3.72534900	0.51007500	-0.93990100		
H	-2.83404800	1.69759500	-1.33960000		
O	-2.01784400	1.47274100	2.02237900		
H	-2.41980800	1.39805600	1.14184000		
H	-1.33125300	0.79444900	2.00758900		
O	-2.17825000	-1.52984900	1.17992600		
H	-1.58384300	-1.60023700	1.93690000		
H	-2.89696300	-0.96565100	1.49169300		
O	-1.50764900	-1.85001300	-1.87570800		
H	-0.90445100	-1.78213300	-2.62516900		
H	-1.21758100	-2.64262500	-1.40685900		
Name				[Cu(A')(H ₂ O) ₄] ⁺ (site O) (water)	
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy	
O	-1.22088800	2.18624200	0.65622900	Zero-point correction=	0.268486 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.45618700	-0.92895800	-0.18869400	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.289593
C	-0.51738100	-0.07241800	0.14048500	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.290537
C	-1.89062400	-0.66114500	0.34798700	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.220518
C	-0.27509800	1.31742600	0.31425800	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-2386.641748
C	1.71561700	-0.50125100	-0.36111600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-2386.620641
C	-2.36653200	-0.59403000	1.80262300	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-2386.619697
C	1.04632700	1.74581000	0.13992900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-2386.689716
C	2.04318800	0.84011600	-0.19533300		
C	2.74547800	-1.52783200	-0.74415500		
H	-1.85423900	-1.70208400	0.02257000		
H	-2.62121100	-0.16115700	-0.29663700		
H	-3.36789200	-1.02084400	1.89750300		
H	-1.69437700	-1.16174200	2.45110800		
H	-2.39954100	0.43497400	2.16530100		
H	1.27175400	2.79922700	0.27255100		
H	3.06710500	1.17022300	-0.33016200		

H	2.76525100	-2.34587800	-0.02005300	
H	2.51470400	-1.95984400	-1.72169900	
H	3.74041600	-1.08389500	-0.79254400	
Cu	-3.01791200	2.29956300	-0.11340000	
O	-4.96218900	1.64197600	-0.45018200	
O	-3.35496500	4.44588300	-0.86098300	
O	-2.39477300	1.75745100	-2.02816100	
O	-3.61274300	2.83013200	1.81167600	
H	-5.16254100	0.97260000	0.21806900	
H	-5.01804900	1.18579600	-1.30010000	
H	-3.39248900	5.01980900	-0.08613700	
H	-2.56317700	4.72472600	-1.33682700	
H	-2.61589000	2.46503200	-2.64848600	
H	-2.87399400	0.97968100	-2.34364400	
H	-2.79365100	2.83179900	2.32638300	
H	-3.95147300	3.73410900	1.84894100	
Name				[Cu(HA)₂(H₂O)₂]²⁺(site N) (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	3.53834500	-1.26146900	0.60046500	Zero-point correction= 0.413454 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.44745400	0.47133900	0.01993000	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.440487
C	1.32592400	-0.47571300	0.38538400	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.441431
C	0.81000700	-1.78166500	0.91166800	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.357798
C	2.69784000	-0.25271500	0.23560000	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2675.492611
C	0.85298600	1.66294900	-0.46177700	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2675.465578
C	0.68246100	-2.82512400	-0.20439500	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -2675.464634
C	3.14053800	0.95917500	-0.27149800	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -2675.548267
C	2.20741500	1.92620300	-0.61595800	
C	-0.20280600	2.67987700	-0.77529900	
H	-0.16165900	-1.60957900	1.38301500	
H	1.48614700	-2.14736600	1.68611300	
H	0.26827100	-3.75491300	0.19061500	
H	0.02105900	-2.46469900	-0.99543100	
H	1.65834300	-3.04117000	-0.64443600	
H	4.20434700	1.13830200	-0.38986200	
H	2.52477900	2.88479700	-1.00558700	
H	-1.00555400	2.23725500	-1.37290300	
H	-0.64394200	3.05886100	0.15119400	
H	0.22197700	3.51855400	-1.32540300	
H	4.45478500	-0.99502100	0.45101100	
Cu	-1.56497000	0.05840200	0.01685900	
O	-1.41781500	-0.42186800	-1.98253500	
H	-1.91981100	-1.20738100	-2.24184200	
H	-0.50903800	-0.58110700	-2.27354600	
O	-1.73194400	0.79123300	1.93338600	
H	-1.11872100	0.35175500	2.53903700	
H	-2.61138400	0.68063100	2.32056200	
O	-6.74138700	1.27110600	-0.24726900	
N	-3.59013800	-0.43678700	0.03400700	
C	-4.50028800	0.54344900	-0.09590100	
C	-4.03905300	1.95772000	-0.29501000	
C	-5.86541700	0.23761200	-0.09303000	
C	-3.96038800	-1.72357300	0.19508600	
C	-3.90898000	2.29583500	-1.78465900	
C	-6.26970400	-1.07802000	0.06720900	

C	-5.30613500	-2.06427000	0.21409500	
C	-2.88122200	-2.75014200	0.36747800	
H	-3.07960100	2.10382100	0.20720400	
H	-4.75295800	2.63429200	0.17682200	
H	-3.55466500	3.32079300	-1.91018400	
H	-3.19896300	1.62440800	-2.27222000	
H	-4.87331000	2.20036200	-2.28860400	
H	-7.32747900	-1.32007600	0.07899200	
H	-5.59312300	-3.09925900	0.34748500	
H	-2.22240600	-2.75991100	-0.50549500	
H	-2.27266400	-2.51450700	1.24559600	
H	-3.31093300	-3.74260700	0.49417000	
H	-7.64864600	0.94026100	-0.21293100	
Name				[Cu(HA)₂(H₂O)₂]⁺ (site N) (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	3.52258600	-1.04124100	0.85262400	Zero-point correction= 0.407798 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.42414100	0.51520100	-0.11831700	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.436660
C	1.30389700	-0.35496600	0.40291700	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.437605
C	0.77817300	-1.62769500	0.99897400	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.347933
C	2.67731800	-0.10398300	0.33034900	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2675.648316
C	0.84090400	1.65121300	-0.71145600	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2675.619454
C	0.62285800	-2.70227900	-0.08253500	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -2675.618509
C	3.12533100	1.06630900	-0.26251900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -2675.708181
C	2.19542800	1.95134100	-0.78662700	
C	-0.20320400	2.55777000	-1.29121500	
H	-0.19030800	-1.41758400	1.46198000	
H	1.45314000	-1.97565600	1.78173900	
H	0.18308800	-3.61045600	0.33461700	
H	-0.02775600	-2.34169700	-0.88508200	
H	1.59340300	-2.95416000	-0.51656000	
H	4.18954200	1.27296000	-0.31374000	
H	2.51521300	2.87174800	-1.25822700	
H	-0.67144200	2.08800100	-2.16139200	
H	-0.98873600	2.75333400	-0.55673000	
H	0.23696800	3.50426300	-1.60406200	
H	4.43769100	-0.75144000	0.74215200	
Cu	-1.57115000	0.03580500	-0.11718900	
O	-1.32614800	-0.70860700	-2.94791000	
H	-1.63785900	-1.33283100	-2.28078300	
H	-0.60539300	-0.24463100	-2.50362500	
O	-2.25704800	0.11824700	3.04482700	
H	-1.51755400	-0.49411300	3.13088100	
H	-2.63093900	-0.08495200	2.17793900	
O	-6.67961000	1.39194100	-0.07999300	
N	-3.56638400	-0.41003600	0.06669000	
C	-4.45409100	0.59620900	-0.00253800	
C	-3.93393600	1.99435600	-0.17129700	
C	-5.82655100	0.33144800	0.02947700	
C	-3.97160100	-1.68831700	0.20232100	
C	-3.70889400	2.31412800	-1.65283500	
C	-6.26396900	-0.97650100	0.17303200	
C	-5.32556100	-1.99364700	0.26373200	
C	-2.91434800	-2.74839500	0.28029600	
H	-2.99340200	2.08311900	0.38187100	

H	-4.64077000	2.70256600	0.26245800	
H	-3.29152400	3.31603100	-1.77194000	
H	-3.01190400	1.59771300	-2.09592000	
H	-4.65068400	2.26352300	-2.20448100	
H	-7.32771600	-1.18814800	0.21345500	
H	-5.63874400	-3.02311500	0.38116100	
H	-2.38814500	-2.83462200	-0.67486700	
H	-2.17772700	-2.49411800	1.04741600	
H	-3.35506500	-3.71600900	0.51907600	
H	-7.59394300	1.08202500	-0.04093900	
Name				[Cu(A⁻)₂(H₂O)₂] (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	-2.02506600	1.62764900	-1.21498600	Zero-point correction= 0.383269 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.14247400	-0.98606400	0.02809600	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.411285
C	-0.92064200	-0.35943200	-0.48164700	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.412229
C	-2.14485600	-1.17894600	-0.78629300	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.321513
C	-0.95223000	1.04240000	-0.68971200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2674.598177
C	1.23725700	-0.28840700	0.37220100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2674.570161
C	-3.19614200	-1.03732900	0.32097600	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -2674.569217
C	0.19047200	1.75895400	-0.32045700	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -2674.659932
C	1.28722300	1.09246000	0.21248300	
C	2.39557100	-1.06267300	0.93770700	
H	-1.84870800	-2.22479900	-0.88433800	
H	-2.57488800	-0.85982100	-1.73889100	
H	-4.08330900	-1.63409000	0.09749900	
H	-2.79148700	-1.37509100	1.27840100	
H	-3.50778900	0.00459600	0.43073400	
H	0.20013900	2.83689300	-0.45625900	
H	2.17789100	1.63880800	0.50174100	
H	2.09664100	-1.60140100	1.84056900	
H	2.75429300	-1.80260500	0.21755900	
H	3.22336300	-0.39919200	1.19025200	
Cu	-2.64180800	3.33732200	-0.52386300	
O	-2.39604500	2.74165100	1.47503700	
O	-3.18291600	3.94364300	-2.44318500	
H	-2.51849200	1.79061200	1.59879000	
H	-3.08033000	3.17203700	2.00493600	
H	-3.38432900	3.19702700	-3.02175300	
H	-3.98674100	4.47884900	-2.41117400	
O	-3.23378300	5.06711200	0.16413800	
N	-6.18387100	6.89211500	1.15883400	
C	-4.90831900	6.57062700	0.94282200	
C	-3.84930000	7.54502700	1.38020300	
C	-4.51635000	5.33297700	0.36319000	
C	-7.16566000	6.03577300	0.82664300	
C	-3.22635300	7.12956500	2.71844000	
C	-5.54898500	4.44943300	0.02603900	
C	-6.87429400	4.80162000	0.25884100	
C	-8.57880100	6.47341600	1.09561600	
H	-4.30203000	8.53368500	1.47355700	
H	-3.06746300	7.60370600	0.61881700	
H	-2.44100200	7.82716900	3.01767900	
H	-3.98533900	7.11416000	3.50455000	
H	-2.78740700	6.13112800	2.64998700	

H	-5.29342900	3.48929100	-0.41650900	
H	-7.67785200	4.12118600	0.00028900	
H	-8.72341900	6.68494500	2.15821800	
H	-8.81258800	7.38786100	0.54413900	
H	-9.28968700	5.70162800	0.79831900	
Name				[Cu(A⁻)₃(H₂O)]⁻ (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	-2.32233000	1.36054400	-0.38512200	Zero-point correction= 0.525211 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.34822300	-0.96032500	0.35876300	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.560834
C	-0.86284700	-0.47374900	0.07853500	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.561778
C	-2.01275600	-1.44446700	0.04241900	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.456767
C	-1.09918000	0.90899800	-0.15016800	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -3038.971409
C	1.41157200	-0.14145600	0.41851900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -3038.935786
C	-2.77532200	-1.46872100	1.37152500	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -3038.934842
C	0.02643000	1.74191300	-0.13007200	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -3039.039853
C	1.28006100	1.21891500	0.16245900	
C	2.73909100	-0.76183200	0.75743100	
H	-1.61980000	-2.43894000	-0.17769900	
H	-2.69720700	-1.16884900	-0.76369600	
H	-3.62794100	-2.15051300	1.32240700	
H	-2.12180500	-1.79883200	2.18338100	
H	-3.14760900	-0.47194200	1.62054200	
H	-0.10593900	2.80266300	-0.32613400	
H	2.15228200	1.86249500	0.19276300	
H	2.70396400	-1.23725100	1.74124900	
H	3.00432500	-1.53328900	0.02982100	
H	3.53039900	-0.01134800	0.76706900	
Cu	-2.77357400	3.24768600	-0.01310000	
O	-3.17762800	3.39673500	-2.07300800	
H	-3.52919400	2.56459500	-2.41416800	
H	-3.85113900	4.06540700	-2.25256200	
O	-3.42901300	5.10826900	0.17179700	
N	-6.46161200	6.86038100	1.04753800	
C	-5.17083400	6.58092800	0.85818900	
C	-4.16145400	7.61161900	1.28837700	
C	-4.72306800	5.35046000	0.30332400	
C	-7.40656900	5.97001800	0.70041900	
C	-3.52436400	7.27091100	2.64041200	
C	-5.72241200	4.44829600	-0.08646900	
C	-7.06247500	4.75484900	0.11950000	
C	-8.83877600	6.35262800	0.95422100	
H	-4.66545100	8.57780300	1.35241500	
H	-3.37703300	7.69342900	0.53112600	
H	-2.82868100	8.05494600	2.94840200	
H	-4.29132100	7.17314500	3.41340500	
H	-2.97275400	6.32960500	2.58693100	
H	-5.42996800	3.49980300	-0.52958400	
H	-7.83795800	4.05335700	-0.16789000	
H	-9.00404800	6.55431600	2.01576800	
H	-9.10171200	7.25956200	0.40326000	
H	-9.51630600	5.55538900	0.64620800	
O	-2.13932000	3.24995100	1.87425700	
N	-3.69009100	0.75396700	3.99813700	
C	-3.54135200	1.75738000	3.12833200	

C	-4.78688200	2.43224500	2.62079700	
C	-2.26859100	2.21540100	2.69216800	
C	-2.61319400	0.11504700	4.48116900	
C	-5.04752000	3.77379100	3.31498200	
C	-1.15580400	1.53547400	3.20526700	
C	-1.32788800	0.48749800	4.10121800	
C	-2.85907400	-1.03480500	5.41861500	
H	-5.63388900	1.76172800	2.78006300	
H	-4.69442100	2.59504200	1.54209700	
H	-5.94537700	4.25459500	2.91561500	
H	-5.18809800	3.62542800	4.38913400	
H	-4.20579900	4.45446400	3.17166000	
H	-0.16277000	1.84483900	2.89319300	
H	-0.47048500	-0.04381800	4.50001300	
H	-3.48422700	-0.72563400	6.25989700	
H	-3.38114400	-1.84521900	4.90111500	
H	-1.92038900	-1.42848400	5.81039600	
Name				[Cu(A⁻)₄]²⁻ (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	-2.30422300	0.78055900	0.11847100	Zero-point correction= 0.665703 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.31850700	-1.64817500	0.64086000	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.709808
C	-0.89135700	-1.10359900	0.50054300	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.710752
C	-2.08694800	-1.99675700	0.69394700	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.585393
C	-1.08852500	0.27709000	0.21328500	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -3403.338182
C	1.42251400	-0.89516900	0.49821900	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -3403.294077
C	-2.65598400	-1.87577100	2.11180200	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -3403.293132
C	0.07494500	1.03883500	0.02976700	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -3403.418491
C	1.32747000	0.45481800	0.18050700	
C	2.74996700	-1.57801300	0.68307500	
H	-1.78597900	-3.02823500	0.50050500	
H	-2.86069600	-1.73077000	-0.03062500	
H	-3.54242900	-2.50294700	2.23522200	
H	-1.91316900	-2.18607100	2.85177900	
H	-2.93552700	-0.84130700	2.32572000	
H	-0.02284700	2.09334500	-0.21530100	
H	2.22838700	1.04456500	0.05103700	
H	2.83143100	-2.00296000	1.68707500	
H	2.86814600	-2.39778900	-0.03048500	
H	3.57317200	-0.87698500	0.53968700	
Cu	-2.57840000	2.77052500	0.21101800	
O	-3.43702100	4.55731500	0.49348000	
N	-5.79740900	6.62207900	-1.29680700	
C	-4.74628200	6.24504500	-0.56741700	
C	-3.80189600	7.31290000	-0.08557700	
C	-4.51549200	4.89224800	-0.18709300	
C	-6.69966000	5.71134600	-1.70275000	
C	-4.10796700	7.70685400	1.36440100	
C	-5.49093800	3.96580800	-0.57728300	
C	-6.57974200	4.37517900	-1.33862600	
C	-7.83107400	6.20298200	-2.56366000	
H	-3.89184500	8.18375100	-0.73899100	
H	-2.77402500	6.94807300	-0.15092300	
H	-3.40698400	8.46415900	1.72292100	
H	-5.11959100	8.11209600	1.44789800	

H	-4.03595400	6.83663800	2.02250100	
H	-5.36068700	2.92212000	-0.30217600	
H	-7.32579500	3.65775400	-1.66321500	
H	-8.38954900	6.99603900	-2.05964800	
H	-7.44932900	6.61555100	-3.50205900	
H	-8.52152900	5.39304500	-2.80246800	
O	-1.77099700	2.89685600	2.04876100	
N	-3.39247500	0.73489600	4.46667500	
C	-3.21730200	1.63941100	3.49906000	
C	-4.44164400	2.34349200	2.97691000	
C	-1.93497700	1.97016000	2.97687800	
C	-2.33948100	0.07613100	4.97599700	
C	-4.57269400	3.76918000	3.52569800	
C	-0.84787100	1.27205200	3.52198600	
C	-1.04935800	0.32897100	4.52270100	
C	-2.62193700	-0.96836400	6.02054100	
H	-5.32024400	1.75952900	3.25791200	
H	-4.40907400	2.37703200	1.88293500	
H	-5.42344000	4.28459100	3.07155400	
H	-4.72476200	3.74784600	4.60807400	
H	-3.67405700	4.35398200	3.31888500	
H	0.14948200	1.48426600	3.14786700	
H	-0.21151100	-0.21607400	4.94396600	
H	-3.21323400	-0.55252300	6.83996700	
H	-3.19394900	-1.79538200	5.58865600	
H	-1.69586800	-1.37276800	6.43119700	
O	-2.64377100	2.82612400	-1.78776800	
N	-3.80422900	5.31257300	-4.14384800	
C	-3.68057300	4.16351200	-3.47601900	
C	-4.58709400	3.02687800	-3.86551500	
C	-2.70520200	3.96495000	-2.45990800	
C	-2.98554300	6.34322100	-3.87110700	
C	-3.88676100	2.05810600	-4.82537800	
C	-1.82867000	5.02992600	-2.22497800	
C	-1.97186000	6.22128700	-2.92740400	
C	-3.22033200	7.62399000	-4.62418400	
H	-5.48231600	3.43939200	-4.33676500	
H	-4.90063200	2.48607900	-2.96997600	
H	-4.54497000	1.22881600	-5.09464100	
H	-3.59200400	2.57071100	-5.74455600	
H	-2.98701800	1.64218100	-4.36517400	
H	-1.05904500	4.91625900	-1.46667600	
H	-1.31011900	7.05878200	-2.73432300	
H	-3.17308000	7.45725700	-5.70339900	
H	-4.21208800	8.02616200	-4.39728500	
H	-2.47704100	8.37644700	-4.35770000	
Name				[Cu(H₂A)(H₂O)₃]³⁺ (site N) (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	-2.65936300	1.56469500	0.45842900	Zero-point correction= 0.271138 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.30166100	-0.33139500	0.99174400	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.290375
C	-0.99875600	-0.05189000	0.77412000	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.291320
C	-1.98195300	-1.17441900	0.70501000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.223944
C	-1.35229600	1.29100600	0.67141200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2311.086297
C	1.30265300	0.56782900	1.07646000	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2311.067059

C	-2.71903600	-1.34785500	2.03900400	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-2311.066115
C	-0.36709900	2.26825600	0.78601300	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-2311.133490
C	0.95608600	1.90619900	0.98744000		
C	2.69727100	0.06776300	1.25114900		
H	-1.45391300	-2.09295600	0.43860000		
H	-2.69489300	-0.95406800	-0.09142400		
H	-3.44098700	-2.16132300	1.95786800		
H	-2.01534100	-1.58699400	2.83834600		
H	-3.25429300	-0.43575500	2.30820300		
H	-0.64769600	3.31365200	0.71039200		
H	1.73087200	2.65700300	1.06980400		
H	3.22834400	0.69523300	1.96670200		
H	2.70601600	-0.96462700	1.60264700		
H	3.23160700	0.11908000	0.29830100		
H	-2.79284400	2.51894300	0.37889800		
H	0.55225400	-1.32023400	1.05167000		
Cu	1.12511300	-0.29793200	-2.09965500		
O	1.82971200	-2.03188000	-1.39724300		
H	2.52250800	-1.88763100	-0.73695700		
H	1.14155300	-2.54800600	-0.95416100		
O	0.46017600	-1.05056600	-3.88048300		
H	1.00050000	-1.79474500	-4.17723300		
H	0.50727100	-0.39008700	-4.58440800		
O	0.51638900	1.56977400	-2.40327600		
H	-0.42109900	1.67807100	-2.18948600		
H	0.98958100	2.20485700	-1.84789000		
Name				[Cu(H₂A)(H₂O)₃]³⁺ (site O) (water)	
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy	
O	-0.40803100	-0.10111200	-1.26691800	Zero-point correction=	0.273322 (Hartree/Particle)
N	2.82198000	0.69063000	0.04019600	Thermal correction to Energy=	0.291742
C	1.57066800	0.87348200	-0.42554600	Thermal correction to Enthalpy=	0.292687
C	1.00762200	2.25623300	-0.46699700	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy=	0.228258
C	0.88482100	-0.26513300	-0.82264600	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies=	-2311.092545
C	3.46628300	-0.49147800	0.13529500	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies=	-2311.074125
C	0.03840200	2.51034500	0.69226500	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies=	-2311.073180
C	1.48647200	-1.51192900	-0.75029600	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies=	-2311.137609
C	2.78515100	-1.62384700	-0.27549800		
C	4.85684400	-0.48176300	0.66912900		
H	0.49240200	2.38423100	-1.42068900		
H	1.83403100	2.96809200	-0.43247300		
H	-0.29737500	3.54752100	0.66845300		
H	-0.84164200	1.86894400	0.61113900		
H	0.52282900	2.32504200	1.65362900		
H	0.93443800	-2.38797900	-1.07371700		
H	3.27588000	-2.58541000	-0.21644400		
H	5.48649800	0.17464000	0.06460300		
H	4.86112200	-0.10842400	1.69562100		
H	5.26632000	-1.48927700	0.65211800		
H	-0.59646100	-0.73058500	-1.98189600		
H	3.33169400	1.52617800	0.33215200		
Cu	-2.05109100	-0.28821200	0.06925300		
O	-3.19924100	0.10538800	-1.54732000		
H	-4.12770900	-0.11777900	-1.39607800		
H	-2.93595100	-0.36528600	-2.34978100		

O	-3.65311500	-0.50986200	1.31523000	
H	-4.44157300	-0.04307900	1.00786900	
H	-3.45965100	-0.16394700	2.19658300	
O	-0.92321100	-0.66706100	1.71057800	
H	-0.44210900	-1.50219800	1.62496900	
H	-0.24377600	0.00876500	1.84743700	
Name				[Cu(H₂A)(H₂O)₄]³⁺ (site N) (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	-1.85350000	-1.53048700	-1.57236000	Zero-point correction= 0.296139 (Hartree/Particle)
N	-1.08085700	1.39814600	0.38465700	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.318221
C	-1.65488400	0.21212100	0.08894700	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.319165
C	-2.59723200	-0.39579100	1.07867500	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.246584
C	-1.34891200	-0.34563500	-1.15011200	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2387.521229
C	-0.23127000	2.08657300	-0.39957300	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2387.499148
C	-4.05977500	-0.17287100	0.67330600	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -2387.498204
C	-0.47181600	0.32167200	-2.00209800	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -2387.570785
C	0.08915900	1.53042400	-1.62704400	
C	0.26893400	3.40068400	0.09683100	
H	-2.40420500	0.03906700	2.06096600	
H	-2.38032700	-1.46545000	1.16012500	
H	-4.71868700	-0.64201900	1.40471600	
H	-4.28622900	0.89380900	0.63346800	
H	-4.26880200	-0.60740500	-0.30680200	
H	-0.22958800	-0.13210600	-2.95705000	
H	0.77744400	2.05189600	-2.27883200	
H	0.45467300	3.36551200	1.17167500	
H	1.18810700	3.66680000	-0.42185000	
H	-0.47872800	4.17409300	-0.09794200	
H	-2.38054100	-1.96689900	-0.88965200	
H	-1.30196000	1.79822600	1.29739100	
Cu	1.44347800	-0.69541600	0.40353000	
O	0.33761300	-0.93735300	2.09340700	
H	-0.14602200	-1.77461400	2.09035600	
H	0.89497600	-0.95186200	2.88310300	
O	2.19346200	1.05881100	1.13450200	
H	1.67196500	1.40857000	1.86995100	
H	3.08984000	0.94391800	1.47846700	
O	2.70309000	-0.42034900	-1.17426300	
H	2.83705600	0.51885700	-1.36255300	
H	2.31231300	-0.79442200	-1.97588700	
O	0.76113900	-2.47424500	-0.36551200	
H	1.45552700	-3.14700400	-0.33571500	
H	0.51867700	-2.39299700	-1.29870700	
Name				[Cu(H₂A)(H₂O)₄]³⁺ (site O) (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	-0.28194600	0.39077600	-1.27619700	Zero-point correction= 0.296667 (Hartree/Particle)
N	2.84154300	0.28079600	0.52214700	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.318622
C	1.67582300	0.78816600	0.07226500	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.319566
C	1.31069700	2.18417200	0.46283500	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.247557
C	0.93326300	-0.01635100	-0.78062700	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2387.512529
C	3.34165700	-0.93656800	0.23062800	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2387.490574
C	1.84679300	3.19875800	-0.55600900	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -2387.489630
C	1.40042400	-1.27498200	-1.13421900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -2387.561639
C	2.60296600	-1.73800700	-0.62360500	

C	4.63296100	-1.32808100	0.86248500	
H	1.71728800	2.38729700	1.45558300	
H	0.22216300	2.25489000	0.53140700	
H	1.56432900	4.20726200	-0.25279300	
H	2.93534500	3.14402700	-0.61383100	
H	1.43623200	3.00659100	-1.55013600	
H	0.81583600	-1.88112700	-1.81675200	
H	2.98052800	-2.71603500	-0.88850500	
H	5.36252100	-0.52127800	0.77396400	
H	4.47554300	-1.53309400	1.92444300	
H	5.02291300	-2.22441500	0.38484600	
H	-0.32544500	1.35455500	-1.37934000	
H	3.38909400	0.87770900	1.14506400	
Cu	-2.10519800	-0.20474900	-0.17798400	
O	-1.71140600	-2.16119900	-0.50479700	
H	-1.43842600	-2.32991000	-1.41671900	
H	-0.99141800	-2.48745500	0.05215500	
O	-3.86239300	-0.76756100	0.74394100	
H	-3.95851000	-0.32900200	1.59995900	
H	-3.86623200	-1.71541100	0.93160700	
O	-2.69169400	1.74592200	-0.25762800	
H	-2.09861700	2.31191100	0.25465800	
H	-3.56788100	1.86005700	0.13512500	
O	-1.03429100	-0.13339400	1.84932400	
H	-0.59535200	0.69136300	2.09054600	
H	-1.73362800	-0.24477300	2.50553700	
Name				[Cu(A⁻)(H₂O)₃]⁺ (site O) (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	-2.31893500	1.20766300	-0.87059400	Zero-point correction= 0.242624 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.49199300	-0.93274400	-0.10171800	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.261962
C	-0.73546100	-0.52651500	-0.43370700	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.262907
C	-1.78839600	-1.57713400	-0.65653000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.195666
C	-1.08575000	0.84462900	-0.52937300	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2310.227235
C	1.45587900	-0.03477600	0.16010800	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2310.207897
C	-2.67428400	-1.74671400	0.58344800	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -2310.206953
C	-0.07198000	1.76897300	-0.25659400	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -2310.274193
C	1.19962200	1.33002200	0.09090900	
C	2.81125100	-0.56808000	0.53329400	
H	-1.29411100	-2.52168500	-0.89021400	
H	-2.40916500	-1.30067700	-1.51233100	
H	-3.44240100	-2.50488900	0.41559700	
H	-2.07381200	-2.05508800	1.44287700	
H	-3.17367100	-0.80781900	0.83691300	
H	-0.30092800	2.82978500	-0.31811400	
H	1.98876700	2.04153700	0.30615100	
H	2.74990700	-1.18243800	1.43533700	
H	3.21374900	-1.19630600	-0.26534600	
H	3.51341400	0.24559400	0.71860600	
Cu	-3.07012300	2.89072100	-0.23456600	
O	-2.79730300	2.30429400	1.72772400	
O	-3.31068400	3.50386200	-2.18957300	
O	-3.99178500	4.61815900	0.32433000	
H	-2.81175300	1.33861500	1.77924600	
H	-3.50598000	2.61285800	2.30774200	

H	-3.29072600	2.72541300	-2.76199400	
H	-4.15622300	3.93997700	-2.35821100	
H	-3.67419100	5.37931600	-0.17934900	
H	-3.83202000	4.82724600	1.25413000	
Name				[Cu(A⁻)(H₂O)₃]⁺ (site N) (water)
Cartesian Coordinates				Frequency and Energy
O	3.68707200	-1.46995800	0.09021900	Zero-point correction= 0.238786 (Hartree/Particle)
N	0.67661900	0.42718200	0.20741200	Thermal correction to Energy= 0.260237
C	1.49299600	-0.61404400	0.27548100	Thermal correction to Enthalpy= 0.261181
C	0.90224500	-1.96337400	0.51102000	Thermal correction to Gibbs Free Energy= 0.188518
C	2.93490400	-0.47105600	0.06931800	Sum of electronic and zero-point Energies= -2310.188875
C	1.16391800	1.66792600	-0.02358100	Sum of electronic and thermal Energies= -2310.167424
C	0.36405600	-2.54816000	-0.80384800	Sum of electronic and thermal Enthalpies= -2310.166480
C	3.42439100	0.86247400	-0.16003900	Sum of electronic and thermal Free Energies= -2310.239143
C	2.54719500	1.90428800	-0.19985500	
C	0.17429600	2.77861200	-0.06436600	
H	0.08493900	-1.85068400	1.22842500	
H	1.65593700	-2.62536700	0.93590400	
H	-0.09679400	-3.52018100	-0.61930200	
H	-0.38792400	-1.88303300	-1.23774400	
H	1.17166700	-2.67918000	-1.52749100	
H	4.49043100	0.99859100	-0.30170500	
H	2.88283200	2.91915400	-0.37278100	
H	-0.67002700	2.50232200	-0.70368300	
H	-0.22264700	2.94267000	0.94407800	
H	0.62578500	3.70290000	-0.42048000	
Cu	-1.41755700	0.12263400	0.18911400	
O	-2.41361500	-0.08456000	-1.85618900	
H	-2.51261500	-1.04167200	-1.93100200	
H	-1.79071900	0.14912200	-2.55433600	
O	-2.61492600	-1.64497300	0.86211000	
H	-3.33280000	-1.74914400	0.22579900	
H	-2.09978600	-2.45716200	0.78472100	
O	-2.93739600	1.57933700	0.94775500	
H	-2.49216100	2.35405300	1.31038800	
H	-3.40319300	1.18849600	1.69646000	

References

1. M. G. Evans and M. Polanyi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 875-894.
2. H. Eyring, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1935, **3**, 107-115.
3. D. G. Truhlar, W. L. Hase and J. T. Hynes, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **87**, 2664-2682.
4. T. Furuncuoglu, I. Ugur, I. Degirmenci and V. Aviyente, *Macromolecules*, 2010, **43**, 1823-1835.
5. E. Vélez, J. Quijano, R. Notario, E. Pabón, J. Murillo, J. Leal, E. Zapata and G. Alarcón, *J. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 2009, **22**, 971-977.
6. E. Pollak and P. Pechukas, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 2984-2991.
7. A. Fernández-Ramos, B. A. Ellingson, R. Meana-Pañeda, J. M. Marques and D. G. Truhlar, *Theor. Chem. Acc.*, 2007, **118**, 813-826.
8. C. Eckart, *Phy. Rev.*, 1930, **35**, 1303.
9. R. A. Marcus, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **15**, 155-196.
10. R. A. Marcus, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1993, **65**, 599.
11. Y. Lu, A. Wang, P. Shi and H. Zhang, *PLoS one*, 2017, **12**, e0169773.
12. Y. Lu, A. Wang, P. Shi, H. Zhang and Z. Li, *PLoS one*, 2015, **10**, e0133259.
13. S. F. Nelsen, S. C. Blackstock and Y. Kim, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 677-682.
14. S. F. Nelsen, M. N. Weaver, Y. Luo, J. R. Pladziewicz, L. K. Ausman, T. L. Jentzsch and J. J. O'Konek, *J. Phys. Chem. A*, 2006, **110**, 11665-11676.
15. A. Galano and J. R. Alvarez-Idaboy, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2013, **34**, 2430-2445.
16. F. C. Collins and G. E. Kimball, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1949, **4**, 425-437.
17. M. Von Smoluchowski, *Z. Phys. Chem*, 1917, **92**, 129-168.
18. D. G. Truhlar, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1985, **62**, 104.
19. A. Einstein, *Ann. Phys.*, 1905, **17**, 549-560.
20. G. G. Stokes, *Mathematical and Physical Papers*, University Press, Cambridge, 1905.
21. A. Galano and J. Raúl Alvarez-Idaboy, *Int. J. Quantum Chem.*, 2019, **119**, e25665.
22. Q. V. Vo, T. V. Gon, M. V. Bay and A. Mechler, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2019, **123**, 10672-10679.
23. H. Boulebd, I. Amine Khodja, M. V. Bay, N. T. Hoa, A. Mechler and Q. V. Vo, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2020, DOI: 10.1021/acs.jpcc.0c02439.
24. Y. Okuno, *Chem.: Eur. J.*, 1997, **3**, 212-218.
25. S. Benson, *The foundations of chemical kinetics:*, Malabar, Florida, 1982.
26. C. Iuga, J. R. Alvarez-Idaboy and A. Vivier-Bunge, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2011, **115**, 12234-12246.
27. J. R. Alvarez-Idaboy, L. Reyes and N. Mora-Diez, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2007, **5**, 3682-3689.
28. T. H. Le, T. T. Tran and L. K. Huynh, *Chemom. Intell. Lab. Syst.*, 2018, **172**, 10-16.